

A testbed for harmonisation of multimodal neuroimaging data

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Introduction

Quantitative brain MRI measures are dependent on nuisance factors, e.g. hardware/software between-scanner differences and post-processing options(1,2). Harmonisation seeks to reduce such unwanted non-biological variability(3–5), either explicitly (preprocessing steps), or implicitly (optimising feature extraction). However, there is a lack of objective ways and datasets to evaluate harmonisation. We present a novel comprehensive multimodal neuroimaging harmonisation resource, using a travelling-heads paradigm. We examine how our resource can assist with a) determining the need for harmonisation for different imaging modalities/features, b) evaluating implicit/explicit harmonisation approaches.

Methods

We used 10 travelling subjects to acquire multimodal MRI data, each scanned at 5 different sites on 6 different 3T scanners (all 3 major vendors: Siemens/Philips/GE) and a range of hardware features (Fig 1A,B). 4 subjects had 6 within-scanner repeats. Scanning protocols were guided by the UK BioBank (UKBB) neuroimaging study(6), while respecting scanner/site best practices, covering 5 modalities (T1w/T2w/SWI/dMRI/rfMRI). Sessions were processed using an adapted UKBB pipeline(7), providing session-wise image quality metrics (IQMs) (from MRIQC(8) and eddyQC(9)) and over 4,000 image-derived phenotypes (IDPs) (Fig 1C).

Due to differences in image acceleration/reconstruction across vendors, we could not perfectly match rfMRI protocols. For Ingenia/GE sessions, we acquired 2 rfMRI protocol variants (Fig 1D) and explored their consistency across scanners.

We assessed between-session multimodal IDP similarity using Spearman's rank correlation, correlating session-wise IDPs with all other sessions. Intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) was used to compare within-subject-between-scanner agreement of modality-specific IDPs.

We also used our resource to optimise processing pipelines for 2 exemplar modalities. We tested the hypotheses that dMRI denoising(10) and multimodal(11), rather than unimodal,

anatomical segmentation will reduce repeat-scan variability in tract-specific microstructure and subcortical volumes respectively.

Results

We found that nominally matching acquisition parameters does not necessarily ensure matching of IQMs across scanners/vendors. Considering spatial smoothness and temporal SNR for rfMRI, the GE 3.3mm and Ingenia MB=4 data showed better agreement to the Siemens 2.4mm, MB=8 data (Fig 1D) than more nominally-matched equivalents. This highlights the importance of considering implementation differences across vendors when matching protocols across scanners.

Session-wise IDP correlations (Fig 2A) revealed high within-scanner repeat reliability. This reduced for between-scanner repeats, which also overlapped with the within-scanner-between-subject distribution: between-scanner repeat variability may be as high as variability across different subjects on the same scanner. This suggests that harmonisation approaches are needed to reduce non-biological variance across scanners. Within-subject agreement (ICC) was, overall, higher for anatomical IDPs compared to dMRI/rfMRI (Fig 2B).

We assessed whether certain processing steps increase IDP consistency. We found that multimodal subcortical segmentation (T1w+T2w) reduces volume variability compared to unimodal (T1w) segmentation (Fig 2C). We also found that dMRI denoising, contrary to expectation, did not always reduce tract-wise FA variability across within-subject-within-scanner repeats (Fig 2D), compared to raw data. This was particularly true for inferior tracts (cerebellum, brainstem, uncinate fascicle). We found that regional off-resonance frequency explains some of this behaviour (Fig 2D right), hinting to interactions between denoising and distortion correction.

Conclusion

We have presented a novel harmonisation database, assessed IDP variability across scanners/modalities and evaluated implicit harmonisation approaches. We plan to publicly share this data.

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A) Harmonisation database

B) Demographics and scanner info

	Scanner	Site	Bore size (cm)	Max grad strength (mT/m)	Grad slew rate (T/m/s)	Coil #channels
24-48 years Mean: 32 (std 10)	GE MR750	QMC	60	50	200	32
	Philips Achieva	SPMIC	60	Dual: 40 (80)	200 (100)	32
2 female/ 8 male	Philips Ingenia	SPMIC	70	45	200	32
	Siemens Prisma	FMRIB	60	80	200	32
	Siemens Prisma	WIN-OHBA	60	80	200	64
	Siemens Trio	OCMR	60	45	200	32

C) Data processing

D) rfMRI protocol parameters and quality comparisons

Figure 1. A) The harmonisation database: data from 10 subjects were acquired across 6 different 3T scanners across 5 sites, covering the three common vendors (Siemens, Philips, GE). 4 subjects also completed 6 within-scanner repeat scans, each on a separate scanner (Philips Achieva, Siemens Prisma (32ch), Siemens Prisma (64ch), and Siemens Trio). 5 imaging modalities were acquired in each case. B) Subject demographics and scanner details. C) Data are processed using the UKBB pipeline (Alfaro-Almagro et al, NeuroImage, 2018). rfMRI and dMRI data were additionally processed using MRIQC (Esteban et al, PLOS ONE, 2017) and eddyQC (Bastiani et al., NeuroImage, 2019) respectively. D) The rfMRI protocol details for each scanner, including variants for the GE (different resolution options: 2.4 and 3.3mm isotropic spatial resolution) and Philips Ingenia (different multiband/TR options: MB4/1450ms and MB6/800ms) scanners, and comparisons of their image parameters and quality metrics.

A) Session-wise and within/between scanner/subject comparisons

Comparison of IDPs derived from all modalities (T1w, T2w, SWI, dMRI, rfMRI).

Includes: brain volumes and tissue intensities, dMRI microstructure, and fMRI node amplitudes

B) IDP intraclass correlation coefficients ICC(3,1) for combinations of scanners

C) Multimodal subcortical segmentation improves reliability

D) The effect of denoising on dMRI IDPs

Figure 2. A) Session-wise comparisons of image-derived phenotypes (IDPs). Left: The session-wise Spearman's rank correlation matrix. Each point on the axis represents a single session. Each heatmap entry represents the correlation value between any two sessions. Same-subject sessions are grouped (black-border). For subjects with within-scanner repeat scans, between-scanner sessions are grouped as the first 6 sessions (green-border) and within-scanner sessions are grouped as the final 6 sessions (blue-border). Right: violin plots of the within/between scanner/subject comparisons, extracted from the correlation matrix. B) Swarm plots of the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC(3,1)) quantifying the within-subject modality-specific (left: anatomical, middle: dMRI, right: rfMRI) IDP agreement across scanners for different combinations of scanners. Each dot represents the ICC for a given IDP. C) Boxplots of the within-subject within/between-scanner CoV of subcortical regions of interest (ROIs) volumes. CoV is calculated within/between scanners subject-wise for each ROI and subsequently averaged across subjects such that each box represents the distribution CoV values (each dot an ROI). Unimodal segmentations were performed using FSL's FIRST (Patenaude et al, NeuroImage, 2011). Multimodal segmentations were performed using FSL's MIST (Visser et al, NeuroImage, 2016), trained on all sessions excluding within-scanner repeats. D) The effect of denoising on tract-wise (TBSS) FA IDPs. Left: The relative difference in region-wise CoV before and after denoising. Tract-wise average FA is calculated for each session, before and after denoising. CoV of the tract-wise FA is then calculated across within-scanner repeats for each subject, before and after denoising. The relative difference before/after denoising is calculated and the mean CoV and standard deviation (error bars) across subjects plotted for each tract. Right: Greater CoV is observed in many of the tracts after denoising. To explore this further, we plot the session-wise region-wise CoV against region-wise mean off-resonance frequency (absolute value in Hz) for such regions.